

Quantum Free Particle Wavelength and Period from Relativity and $x - ct$

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It is well known that the free particle quantum wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ implies a wavelength of \hbar/p and a period of \hbar/E . In this note, we consider only the effects of special relativity on x and t (ignoring E and p) and look for a measure of the difference of the two spacetime lengths, x and ct . A linear measure is a problem because it changes under $v \rightarrow -v$ so we consider the form: $x'x' - t't'$. The form $x'x' - t't'$ is a quadratic measure of the difference of the square of two spacetime lengths (here $c=1$). There is, however, a built-in constraint of $v=x'/t'$ and introducing this constraint leads to a linear form: $x'v - t' = t'/g$, where $g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. In other words, the constraint together with the invariance condition leads to the a form for which $x'=x1'+\text{constant}/g$ and $t'=t1'+\text{constant}/g$ satisfy the equation just as well as $x1', t1'$, leading to the idea of a quantum wavelength and period, we argue. The minus in $x'x' - t't'$ arises from considering a difference in the square of spacetime lengths ($c=1$) for a system, (with the quadratic nature handling $v \rightarrow -v$). The linear form alone cannot give rise to the notion of a wavelength and period, so it is the quadratic form which really yields the wavelength and period which appear in quantum mechanics. One may choose the constant to be \hbar/m_0 so as to distinguish between different m_0 values.

$\exp(-Et+px)$ and the Quantum Wavelength and Period

The quantum free particle wavelength $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ immediately gives rise to a wavelength \hbar/p and period \hbar/E based on p and E . We have argued in previous notes that this follows from the degeneracy of the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ for $x=x_0+\hbar*n/p$ and $t=t_0+n*\hbar/E$ with $n=\text{integer}$. Here we wish to start with the idea of only x and ct as spacetime lengths without considering any notion of E and p and try to see why a wavelength and period arise.

Special Relativity

One may consider a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ (at rest) at t . For x and ct being spacetime lengths, one has the difference in the two lengths:

$$0 - ct \quad ((1))$$

T is a running variable so the length increases in time.

Viewing this situation from a frame moving with constant $-v$, one sees a moving object and has an x' and t' described by the Lorentz transformation such that $x'/t'=v$:

$$\begin{aligned} |g(v) \quad v g(v)| \\ |v g(v) \quad g(v)| \quad ((2)) \quad \text{where } g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \end{aligned}$$

If one considers a linear difference between spacetime lengths, then:

$$X' - t' = g(v)v t - t g(v) \quad ((3))$$

This would imply that: $g(v)=1-v$, but this is not the same for v and $-v$ and cannot be the measure desired. One must have a measure which is invariant under $v \rightarrow -v$.

To avoid issues of sign, one may consider the difference:

$$00 - ctct \quad \text{and} \quad x'x' - t't' \quad \text{which yields:} \quad g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}, \quad \text{the Lorentz result} \quad ((4))$$

In other words, we suggest that the main idea is to find a difference between squares of two lengths in spacetime as representing an invariant. The quadratic form is key because $v \rightarrow -v$ must yield the same result.

Another way to view $x'x' - t't'$ as an invariant of the transformation is to consider a kind of unitary transformation which requires a special metric because both t' and x' increase and so one needs a minus sign between them. (This is also clear if one considers the same transformation acting on $(0, mocc)$.) In other words, one has the transformation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} |g & vg| \\ |1 & 0| \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} |g & vg| \\ |0 & -1| \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ t \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} t \\ t \end{pmatrix} \quad ((4b))$$

The quadratic form: $x'x' - t't' = tt \quad (c=1) \quad ((5))$ does not explicitly show the constraint:

$$x'/t'=v \quad ((6))$$

Introducing it creates a linear form: $x'v - t' = tt'/t' = tt/(gt) = t/g \quad ((7))$

It is the form ((7), which results from the quadratic, i.e. difference of the square of lengths, which yields the wavelength and period of quantum mechanics, we argue.

One may see that if $x1'$ and $t1'$ are solutions of ((7)) then so are:

$$x'=x1+\text{constant}/gv \quad \text{and} \quad t'=t1'+\text{constant}/g \quad ((8))$$

In other words, there is an uncertainty in length and time which would not exist for a linear measure, $x'-t'$. The fact that one is forced to use a quadratic measure as an attempt to consider the difference in spacetime lengths (i.e. the difference of squares of lengths) leads to the idea of a wavelength and period which are key in quantum mechanics. One may note that the constant may be \hbar/mo to distinguish between different mo values, leading to \hbar/p and \hbar/E as being the wavelength and period, but the above ideas really follow from considerations of x',t' alone.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that trying to find a measure of the difference in two spacetime lengths, namely x and ct such that this is invariant when seen from a frame moving with

constant $-v$ leads to problems if one uses the linear measure $x'-t'$ ($c=1$) because $v \rightarrow -v$ changes the result. One may try to use a quadratic measure $x'^2 - t'^2$ and $0^2 - t^2$ ($c=1$) to create an invariant, but it is this quadratic form, we argue, which leads to the quantum notion of wavelength and period. One may linearize the quadratic by using the Lorentz transformation result $t' = g(v)t$ where $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ so $x' - vt' = t/g(v)$.

If x_1' and t_1' are solutions to this equation, so are: $x_1' + \text{constant}/(gv)$ and $t_1' + \text{constant}/g$. This leads to uncertainty in x and t or the notion of a wavelength and period. Choosing \hbar/m_0 as the constant leads to the wavelength and period being \hbar/p and \hbar/E .